

Cyber Security in Cloud Computing

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Abstract---Cloud computing cyber security must be offered by the elements that make up its structure. Accurately identifying the hazards associated with this technology is the first step towards improving its cyber security. This research proposes a new cyber security reference model for the cloud system, which is composed of parts that constitute different cloud computing layers. The virtualization and service layers, as well as other crucial elements for ensuring cloud computing cyber security, are not thoroughly covered by the reference models of cloud computing security that are currently available. Additionally, the social media IoT sensor layer, which gathers text data entered by attackers to launch cyberattacks on cloud infrastructure, and cloud computing's cyber resilience issues are not considered. Furthermore, this study investigates cloud computing service models' cyber security concerns and builds an attack model to safeguard cloud systems. It provides an understanding of laws and standards about cloud computing cyber security. Clarification of cloud system cyber security and cyber resilience concepts is given by security aspects. Intelligent cloud systems' cyber resilience architecture is designed. The proposed cyber resilience model has an advantage over the existing one in that it identifies the cloud computing's information security and cyber security elements and combines them to build the cloud systems' cyber resilience aspects.

Keywords---Cloud Computing, Cyber Security, Cyber Resilience, Cyberattack Model, Saas, Paas, and Iaas

I. INTRODUCTION

Platforms for information systems are technical ecosystems or architectures that link consumers with creators and suppliers of related goods and services. Cloud service providers represent a classic example of these kinds of platforms. Specifically, public cloud platforms lower capital requirements and entry barriers by turning fixed expenditures into variable costs for consumers [3]. Through virtualization and multi-tenancy, the ensuing user-side transactions enable providers of Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS) to benefit from scale economies. Amazon Web Service (AWS), Microsoft Azure, and Google Cloud Platform are examples of prototypical IaaS providers. PaaS suppliers include Google App Engine, Oracle Cloud Platform, and SAP Cloud Platform. Salesforce.com, Microsoft Office 365, and Adobe Creative Cloud are a few SaaS providers. Cloud architectures become more vertically integrated as one moves up the multilayered cloud service stack (from IaaS to PaaS to SaaS) since each layer incorporates the services of the ones below it [3]. As one climbs the cloud's layers, the degree of abstraction and complexity likewise rises.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The paper's structure is arranged as follows: The architecture of the suggested cyber security reference model for the intelligent cloud computing system and cyber security model is shown in Section 2. In Section 3, Cybersecurity vulnerabilities in cloud computing systems' service delivery models. The data security issues and attacks are introduced in Section 4 on cloud computing. Cyber security management/ cyber resilience is discussed in Section 5.

The study's contribution and findings conclusions, and acknowledgement are compiled in Section 6.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2. Intelligent cloud computing reference model for cyber security

It is necessary to first outline the architecture of the cloud system to guarantee the cyber security of cloud computing. In this context, major institutions like Microsoft, IBM, and NIST offer reference models for cloud computing. The five key participants in the standard model of cloud computing information systems are the cloud client, cloud provider, cloud auditor, cloud auditor, and cloud broker, according to the NIST organization. Layers named Orchestration, Service, Resource abstraction and management, Physical resources, cloud service administration, and security make up the NIST reference model. Here, the following concerns are taken into account for the cloud computing system's security:

- Verification and approval of clients using cloud services.
- Resources are assigned and allocated for node recovery, updates, and connections.
- Surveillance of digital assets
- Tracking cloud activity and providing performance reports.
- Choosing the service level agreements (SLA) parameters.
- observing the SLA's execution by the established security policy.

IBM has put up another cloud computing reference model. Three roles characterize the cloud computing system, according to IBM's reference model: customer, operator, and cloud service creator. Individual entities, groupings of entities, or organizations can carry out these roles. This architecture covers the physical infrastructure, cloud services, and cloud management platform while taking performance, security, and resilience to failures into common consideration.

Existing reference models for cloud computing security do not account for the social media IoT (Internet of Things) sensor layer, which gathers text data typed by attackers to launch cyberattacks on the cloud infrastructure, or the cyber resilience issues associated with cloud computing. They also do not describe the virtualization and service layers and the critical components for providing the cyber security of cloud computing in detail. Regarding this, the study that is being presented suggests a new cloud computing systems cyber security reference model that consists of elements that make up each cloud computing layer. The following is a representation of the new model (Fig.1).[5]

The cloud consumer and the cloud operator are the two primary subjects of the suggested cloud computing system paradigm. The application layer, service layer, virtualization layer, data transmission layer, physical resources layer, Internet of Things social media sensor layer, cyber security layer, and cyber resilience layer make up this

concept. In the context of the suggested cloud computing system model, the following concerns are taken into account regarding security:

Defect identification

The following are some of the key areas of focus [1]:

- Sensitive Data Privacy;
- Cyberattack Clustering;
- Identity Management;
- Trust Management;
- Anomaly Detection;
- Task Scheduling;
- Risk Assessment;
- Cloud Security Monitoring;
- Identification of cyber threats and CTI data (Cyber Threat Intelligence) from social media texts.

3. Cybersecurity vulnerabilities in cloud computing systems' service delivery models

Three service models are used by cloud computing to offer users a variety of services. Customers can access application platforms, infrastructure resources, and software resources as a service through cloud computing's SaaS (Software as a Service), PaaS (Platform as a Service), and IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) service models. Different security requirements are placed on the cloud environment by each service model.

The lowest fundamental tier of the cloud computing service model stack is called Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS). According to (Fig. 2), the SaaS model is positioned at the top layer of the PaaS model, which is positioned above the IaaS model.

Fig.2 Cloud Computing Architecture [4]

The four tiers of the cloud computing architecture are depicted in Fig. 2: application layer, platform layer, infrastructure layer, and hardware layer. These strata are arranged over one another. Every layer is constructed using the loosely coupled approach with the layers that come before and after it. Each layer is allowed to operate independently because of this characteristic.

Layer of Hardware. The cloud's physical resources are managed by this tier. Physical servers, routers, switches, power, and cooling systems are some examples of these resources.

Layer of Infrastructure. The virtualization layer is another name for this layer. This layer's job is to use virtualization technologies to build a pool of computing and storage resources.

Layer of the Platform. The infrastructure layer is the one above this one. Operating systems are included in this tier.

a layer of applications. Compared to typical apps, the cloud's application layer is different. Auto-scalability in cloud applications allows for cost-effective performance and availability increases.

Certain security-related problems with the service models fall under the purview of the cloud providers, while other issues are the responsibility of the cloud users.

Problems with security in the SaaS model

The SaaS model stores each customer's data in the data center of the SaaS provider next to the data of other customers. To ensure availability, the cloud provider also replicates data to several sites across international borders. Businesses in conventional information systems are aware of data storage guidelines. Nonetheless, there are serious security problems because users are unaware of the guidelines for storing and safeguarding their data in the SaaS model. Here, the introduction of issues like accessibility, software program vulnerabilities, and data leaking causes harm that is both financially and legally significant.

The supplier bears full responsibility for cloud security management under the SaaS model. Apps are the resources that SaaS offers [1]. To create the ideal SaaS model, the following security concerns should be investigated in detail: Data leakage, virtualization vulnerabilities, data security, network security, colocation, data integrity, data segregation, data access control, authentication and authorization, and data secrecy.

Security issues of the PaaS layer

Web application security, data leakage, data security, colocation, data integrity, data segregation, data access control, authentication and authorization, data secrecy, and virtualization vulnerabilities are some examples of data security and network security.

Security issues of the IaaS layer

Users are granted authority over security management through the IaaS layer. The provider's and the customer's security obligations differ greatly depending on the service model. Elastic Compute Cloud, or EC2, is an infrastructure solution from Amazon that gives the provider protection up to the hypervisor. Providers are limited to managing virtualization, environmental, and physical security in this instance. In turn, the client has the power to handle security-related issues about the data, operating system, apps, and IT system [1].

IV. CYBER SECURITY ISSUES AND ATTACKS

Attacks directed at cloud systems include:

Data Breaches: In cloud computing, data is stored in the cloud environment by a variety of users and organizations, and any intrusion into this environment might potentially compromise the data of all cloud users. As a result, the data that is processed, transferred, or kept in a cloud environment is highly valuable. This encompasses security lapses in threat detection, vulnerability mitigation, security intelligence, and other areas as well as breaches brought on by malevolent or careless human actions, targeted attacks, and vulnerabilities related to cloud applications.

Data loss: The loss of data is by far the most common risk connected with cloud computing. Data can be compromised in several ways, for as by removing or changing the original content. In the cloud context, data loss resulting from malware or viruses that impact backup storage, hardware, and data recovery is lethal. Natural calamities, power outages, human mistakes, and hard disc failure can all result in data loss.

Account or service traffic hijacking: The same risks that numerous other web services face can also be posed by thieves or hackers accessing private information linked to accounts and services [2]. Hackers may publish, use, or sell private data, including bank records, images, credit card details, and more. In addition, spying on activities, malware/spyware invasion, social engineering manipulations, and man-in-the-middle attacks are all part of this threat.

Insecure interfaces and application program interfaces (APIs): Virtual machines (VMs), insecure APIs, and interfaces could also be dangerous for the cloud computing environment. The user uses virtual machines (VMs), APIs, and other software interfaces to access cloud services. Because they offer provisioning, management, and activity monitoring, these points of contact are essential parts. Therefore, weaknesses in security at these points result in unauthorized access, illegal authentication, encryption breaches, etc. These dangers result from unpatched software, unstable operating systems (OS), poor key management, weak API credentials, and hypervisor issues [2].

Denial of service (DoS): In a denial-of-service attack, the attacker floods the network with spam in an attempt to exhaust resources by generating pointless traffic. For legitimate users, this scenario may also result in the unavailability of resources and services. Weak network security architecture, open apps, unsecured network protocols, and other factors can all lead to this kind of assault.

Virtualization attack: The best virtualization is programmed with the lay-on architecture, and built-in virtualization architecture requires separately constructed hardware. Modern operating systems have anomalies and enemies, which can lead to vulnerabilities that allow an adversary to take control of the host OS. Once the attacker gains control over the host operating system, the hypervisor is mostly identified as abnormal. Thus, the aggressor will be able to carry out any malicious operations on any of the virtual machines (VMs) that the hypervisor supports thanks to its command and directorial rights.

Cloud malware injection: Attacks such as cloud malware injection attacks (CMIA) are used to obtain access to operator data that is processed and stored on cloud infrastructure [2]. Cross-site scripting and structured query language (SQL) injection attacks are two of the most often used CMIA threats. Vulnerable cloud service providers, like the OpenStack cloud platform, make such attacks conceivable. Adversaries can simply transmit jumbled data from a buffer by abusing a design weakness in modern mainframes with the use of a malicious cipher.

V. CYBER SECURITY MANAGEMENT/ RESILIENCE

It is hard to design systems that are impervious to cyberattacks. Cyber-attacks on information systems are a constant. But these attacks are beyond the reach of current defenses. Cyber resilience appears to be the most promising way to address the emerging issue.

Computer systems' cyber resilience might convey different meanings to various organizations. Maintaining a "never-down system" is important to some of them, while being able to swiftly bounce back from setbacks and incidents is important to others. The ability of a system (network, service, or infrastructure) to deliver and maintain an acceptable level of service even in the face of numerous breakdowns and issues in the regular course of business is known as cyber resilience, according to the organization ENISA [1].

VI. CONCLUSION AND SCOPE FOR FUTURE WORK

The reference models for cloud system cyber security and cyber resilience were presented in this research. The primary elements of the suggested model were the focus of a taxonomy of attacks, and their objectives were deciphered. We examined the dangers, weaknesses, and possibilities associated with cloud computing. Intelligent cloud systems now share a common architecture for cyber security and cyber resilience [1]. The distinct countermeasures to counter cyberattack comprised the functional components of the architecture. Because these were intended to be independent clouds, the intelligent cloud system was able to bounce back from unforeseen failures.

The benefit of this strategy was that the virtualization layer and services—the two key elements required to guarantee cloud computing's cyber security—were not included in the reference models that were already in place. Apart from the Internet of Things sensor layer for social media, which gathers text input entered by attackers to initiate cyberattacks on cloud infrastructure, cloud computing's cyber resilience challenges were not considered at all.

Future research will focus on creating software for "Everything as a Service" models that will guarantee the cyber resilience of intelligent cloud systems. Deep learning-based techniques for detecting SLA violations in the system will be developed in order to effectively monitor the cyber security of cloud services.

A statement of conflicting interests

The authors declare that none of the work reported in this study could have been influenced by any known competing financial interests or personal relationships.

Accessibility of Data

The research detailed in the article did not use any data.

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